

President Barack Obama's Afghan Policy: A Diplomatic Analysis

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ABSTRACT

After the 9/11 attacks on the United States, President George W. Bush promised a swift and decisive war against the Taliban and al-Qaeda. But his misguided policies toward Afghanistan turned the Afghan war into a protracted and deadly conflict. Upon taking office, President Barack Obama pledged to end the Afghan War, which was one of the central foreign policy challenges for his administration. He adopted a new strategy for the Afghanistan war to reverse the Taliban's movements and strengthen the power of the Afghan government. As part of his new strategy, Obama ordered the deployment of additional troops to Afghanistan, to stabilize the country and lay the groundwork for a gradual withdrawal of US troops.

KEYWORDS: Al-Qaida, NATO, Osama bin Laden, Operation Enduring Freedom, War on Terror, Strategic Partnership Agreement, Taliban, AfPak Strategy, Bilateral Security Agreement (BSA), International Security Assistance Force (ISAF).

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
06 June 2026

Available on:
<https://irijsh.com/>

INTRODUCTION

After the September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks on the United States, which were believed to have been plotted by al-Qaeda, President George W. Bush quickly formed a war cabinet and announced a comprehensive plan to defeat the Taliban and al-Qaeda leader Osama bin Laden. On 24 September 2001, as part of his "war on terror", Bush signed an executive order to freeze the assets of the al-Qaeda terrorist group and other organizations that finance terrorist activities. The following day, US Secretary of Defense Donald Rumsfeld changed the name of the counter-terrorism operation to "Operation Enduring Freedom" to bring the national mood into line with the name of the war operation (Becker, 26 September 2001).

On 7 October 2001, President George W. Bush launched "Operation Enduring Freedom" in Afghanistan, after the Taliban refused to hand over bin Laden, who was spending his vast personal wealth to support the Taliban. The United States, with British assistance, began airstrikes against Taliban military installations and al-Qaeda training camps in Afghanistan. In mid-November, with the help of bombings and massive casualties, the Northern Alliance and anti-Taliban forces captured Taliban strongholds, including the capital Kabul. The Taliban regime ended completely on 9 December 2001, when the Taliban and their leader Mollah Omar fled to Kandahar and later to Pakistan. In November, the number of US troops in Afghanistan was 1,300. In the coming weeks, Britain, Turkey, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, France and Poland all expressed their intention to send troops to Afghanistan. The Bush administration periodically increased US troops in Afghanistan to suppress Taliban insurgents (Liptak, 24 August 2021).

After the fall of Kabul, the United Nations established an Afghan interim administration led by Hamid Karzai, a favorite of the United States. On 20 December, the United Nations established the International Security Assistance Force (ISAF) to maintain peace and security in Kabul. The US Congress approved more than \$38 billion as part of Bush's Marshall Plan for the reconstruction of Afghanistan from 2001 to 2009 (US war in Afghanistan 1999-2021). In late 2001, both Afghanistan and the United States revived their diplomatic relations. On 23 May 2005, the United States and Afghanistan signed a Strategic

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Partnership Agreement to ensure long-term US involvement in Afghanistan's security as well as development and prosperity. Among the key points of the agreement was to provide continued access to the critical Bagram Air Base and other military installations for US military forces operating in Afghanistan as may be mutually determined (Al Jazeera, 24 May 2005). After driving most of the insurgents out of Afghanistan, American attention shifted to eliminating al-Qaeda and the Taliban in Pakistan, where the Taliban were reportedly working in alliance with like-minded leaders of religious groups, who now controlled two provinces along the Afghanistan-Pakistan border. Pakistani President Pervez Musharraf promised to hunt down terrorists within Pakistan's borders, but his government was unable to provide full support to the US military. Due to the growing Indian presence in Afghanistan, Pakistani intelligence agencies maintained cooperative relations with Taliban leaders. The Taliban received financial support from some wealthy Arab donors, but most of it came from intelligence agencies in Russia, Iran, and Pakistan who were not happy with the US presence in Afghanistan (Baldauf, 8 May 2003).

In 2003, ISAF shifted its focus from Afghanistan to Iraq, which was considered the main threat to the United States in the 'war on terror'. That same year, Donald Rumsfeld declared victory and the end of the 'major war' campaign in Afghanistan. This announcement coincided with President Bush's 'mission accomplished' declaration of the end of the war in Iraq. At that time, only 8,000 US troops were deployed in Afghanistan as part of the International Security Assistance Force under the NATO supervision. Taking advantage of the US parallel military campaign in Iraq in 2005, the Taliban were able to regroup to continue their guerrilla warfare against US forces and the new Afghan government of President Hamid Karzai. Following Iraqi insurgent tactics, they now began an unequal guerrilla war against the US-led coalition forces. By the summer of 2006, Taliban attacks across Afghanistan had increased dramatically. Between January 2005 and August 2006, there were approximately sixty four attacks against US forces. European countries were reluctant to send more troops due to the increased violence (Shad and Iqbal, December 2021). In March 2007, Bush decided to send 3,500 troops to Afghanistan to accelerate the training of local forces, to double its previous troop numbers to fight the resurgent Taliban (Baker, 11 March 2007).

After 2004, the Bush administration changed its Afghanistan war strategy to a state-building strategy. But this state-building strategy failed miserably due to the consequences of the Bush administration's misguided military strategy. Although President Bush took some of the right steps at the beginning of the Afghan war, by the end of 2008 the war in Afghanistan was going badly, and Bush knew it (Millar, 15 February 2016). In 2008, US commanders on the ground called for the deployment of more troops to implement an effective strategy against the Taliban. But Bush did not respond to their request for an emergency declaration; he only agreed to send additional troops. When Bush left office in January 2009, there were 68,000 troops in Afghanistan. The cost of the Afghan war increased by nearly \$100 billion from 2005 to 2009 (Bilal, Malik, and Jamil, 2022). Due to Bush's misguided approach to Afghanistan, which was characterized as "unilateral, nationalist, conservative, and power-centric," the United States was unable to achieve success in Afghanistan. (Wakil, Mustafa and Shabbir, December 2022). By 2009, there was reasonable reason to conclude that unless American strategy against the Taliban was revised, American forces and their NATO allies would be headed for defeat (Weinbaum, 5 November 2014).

During his presidential campaign, Barack Obama repeatedly criticized the Bush administration's policy of invading and occupying Iraq, but he was equally firm in declaring his support for the US military mission in Afghanistan (Cortright, 2011). Obama also said in his much-quoted speech that "As president, I will make the fight against al Qaeda and the Taliban the highest priority that it should be. This is a battle we have to win." He considered the war in Afghanistan to be more important than Iraq (New York Times, 15 July 2008). Upon taking office in January 2009, President Barack Obama was determined to focus attention on Afghanistan, which, unlike Iraq, was not only a "more legitimate front in the war on terror," but also a huge burden on the US economy (Khan, 2009). The war situation in Afghanistan had deteriorated so much that early in his first term in the White House, Obama was under intense pressure from the "civilian foreign policy hawks and the uniformed military to act decisively and prevent the United States from "losing the war." Despite growing pressure from the American public Obama refused to take any action too quickly. In fact he had to spend several months reviewing strategic goals, questioning assumptions, and debating policy options to find an acceptable end to the Afghan war. As Obama continued to push for additional options from the military and his advisors, a split naturally emerged in the administration. Ultimately, the president supported the option of Defense Secretary Robert Gates, who called for the deployment of an additional 30,000 US troops to focus on both training and population-based counterinsurgency. However, Obama remained steadfast in his preference for a gradual troop withdrawal and insisted that the increase would come with a timetable for withdrawal (Warden, Spring 2013). He introduced two strategies that outlined US objectives in Afghanistan to end the Afghan war and stabilize Afghanistan. Obama announced his first Afghanistan strategy on 27 March 2009 and his second Afghanistan strategy on 1 December 2009. The two strategies, known as the AfPak policy or the policy for Afghanistan and Pakistan, were closely related (Raees, September 2010).

Obama's new strategy was linked to three important US interests. First, the United States had an interest in preventing Afghanistan from once again becoming a safe haven for al-Qaeda, where terrorists planned and trained for attacks against the United States. Second, the United States had an interest in maintaining its international reputation, because if the United States could not defeat the Taliban and al-Qaeda, its credibility internationally would suffer. The third interest of the United States in

Afghanistan was to prevent instability and extremism from spreading to Pakistan; in a worst-case scenario, Islamic extremists with ties to Al Qaeda would gain control of Pakistan's nuclear arsenal. For this reason, President Obama and others described Afghanistan as a war of necessity, not a war of choice (Warden, Spring 2013).

The main objective of the present article, based on information obtained from journals, books, and online newspapers published on various websites, is to analyze the major steps taken by the Obama administration towards Afghanistan. Numerous articles on Obama's Afghan policy have been published in the USA and outside the USA. These writings mention both the positive and negative aspects of his administration's Afghan policy, which the author has attempted to analyze objectively.

OBAMA'S AFGHAN POLICY

When Obama took office in January 2009, there were more than 32,000 Americans serving in Afghanistan, compared to 160,000 in Iraq at the height of the war. Soon after taking office, Obama appointed Richard Holbrooke as his special advisor for Pakistan and Afghanistan, to conduct a thorough review of the Afghan war. Holbrooke's main task was to press both Pakistan and Afghanistan to cooperate with each other, as well as with NATO and the United States, to defeat extremist elements - mainly the Taliban and al-Qaeda in this region (Khan, 2009). Early in his Presidency, Obama approved a long-standing request from US commanders in Afghanistan to send more troops to bolster US forces in Afghanistan. In a written statement released on 17 February 2009, Obama pledged to send an additional 17,000 US troops to Afghanistan by the summer to stabilize the deteriorating situation in Afghanistan (Cooper, 17 February 2009).

On 27 March 2009, after consulting with US allies, he announced a new strategy for the Afghan war, linking success in Afghanistan to a stable Pakistan (Obama's Speech, 27 March 2009). The aim of his strategy was to bring the US intervention in Afghanistan to the logical conclusion of the war. Obama identified three key elements of the new strategy: a military effort to create the conditions for change; a civil uprising that will strengthen affirmative action; and an effective partnership with Pakistan (Munir, 20 December 2010). Afghan President Karzai welcomed the strategy, saying that this plan will bring Afghanistan and the international community closer to success.

President Obama confirmed that without new military strategies and decisive action, US forces risk failure in the war on terror. In May 2009, he replaced General David D. McKiernan, the top military commander in Afghanistan, with a former Special Forces commander Lieutenant General Stanley A. McChrystal a counterinsurgency expert to turn the tide of the war that was going badly for the United States and intensifying the search for Osama bin Laden (McAskill, 11 May 2009). After conducting a secret assessment of the Afghan war, McChrystal submitted a 66-page report to Defense Secretary Robert Gates calling for more troops to be sent to Afghanistan, stating: "We are going to win." General McChrystal warned in his report that if more troops were not sent, the war in Afghanistan would likely be lost (Schmitt, 20 September 2009). In fact, General McChrystal requested 40,000 more troops for the Afghan war. But on 23 June 2010, Obama fired General Stanley A. McChrystal for making derogatory comments about President Obama and senior officials and replaced General David Petraeus, who led the successful campaign in Iraq which inspired McChrystal's new strategy for Afghanistan (McGreal, 24 June 2010).

After a series of meetings beginning in September 2009, Obama announced his second strategy for Afghanistan and Pakistan, which called for broader and more coordinated cooperation to get the job done quickly (Rais, September 2010). As part of his second strategy, on 9 December he announced the deployment of 30,000 additional troops to Afghanistan to reverse the Taliban's advance. To justify his decision, he said, "I am making this decision because I am convinced that our security is at risk in Afghanistan and Pakistan" (Obama's Speech, 1 December 2009). Obama not only announced a troop increase in Afghanistan, but also promised to begin a "conditional" withdrawal of US troops from Afghanistan in July 2011 (DeYoung, 16 December 2010).

THE LONDON CONFERENCE

At the conference on Afghanistan in London on 28 January 2010, which was attended by representatives from seventy countries, the United States and its NATO allies have given clear signals that they are developing an exit strategy and are determined to hand over security responsibility to Kabul within five years (Marquand, 28 January 2010). To achieve this goal, conference delegates set a plan to recruit approximately 171,600 soldiers and 134,000 police officers by October 2011 to help Afghan forces take responsibility for their own security (Borger, 28 January 2010). Another important agenda item at the London summit was a \$500 million peace offer to rehabilitate Taliban fighters, mainly locals, who were willing to break ties with al-Qaeda and renounce violence. The Taliban has dismissed the London conference as a propaganda ploy, saying the summit will fail to produce positive results (Al Jazeera, 29 January 2010). During the meeting, international donors pledged more financial support for Afghanistan's infrastructure and security development but at the same time, they urged the Afghan government to tackle corruption (Borger, 28 January 2010).

OBAMA'S FIRST VISIT TO AFGHANISTAN AS PRESIDENT

On 28 March 2010, Obama made a surprise visit to Afghanistan where he spent a night with American and NATO troops. He was looking for a way to begin withdrawing US troops from Afghanistan before the end of his first term. For this purpose, it was essential to change the Taliban's trajectory and reduce the threat posed by al-Qaeda and other militants on the Afghanistan-Pakistan border. But Afghanistan was proving to be even more difficult than Iraq, as the country lacked basic infrastructure. Moreover, the failure of President Karzai's government to combat corruption was an obstacle to success on the battlefield against the Taliban (MacSkill, 28 March 2010). Therefore, after landing at Bagram Air Base, the headquarters of the International Security Assistance Force's regional command east, Obama flew directly to Kabul to meet Karzai to discuss the Afghan government's progress in strengthening its capacity to govern the country and providing security to its people (CNN, 29 March 2010). After the meeting, Obama pledged continued American assistance to Afghanistan, but he also emphasized good governance and 'anti-corruption efforts' (Rubin and Cooper, 28 March 2010). However, the main purpose of his visit was to boost the morale of American troops ahead of the offensive in Kandahar province, which the US military described as the key point of the conflict (MacSkill, 28 March 2010). In his speech to soldiers, sailors, airmen and Marines at Bagram Air Base, Obama highlighted the sacrifices of US troops in Afghanistan. He pledged to "bleed together and succeed as one nation" (Ahmed, 4 April 2010).

By August 2010, the number of US troops in Afghanistan reached 100,000, alongside 40,000 NATO troops (CNN Editorial Research, 2 October 2023). Yet 2010 was the deadliest year for US troops, with four hundred eighty nine deaths (Munir, 20 December 2010). The surge in US troops in Afghanistan led to some progress in disrupting the Taliban and al-Qaeda, although those successes remain "fragile and counterproductive" (DeYoung, 16 December 2010). Certain elements of the US strategy for Afghanistan and Pakistan were working well and progress had been made in some areas, particularly in Kandahar and Helmand provinces, But that progress was not enough to drive the Taliban and its allies from the Pakistani border (McGreal, 16 December 2010). Therefore, Obama mentioned in his briefing the need for greater cooperation and coordination with Pakistan in eliminating al-Qaeda and Taliban sanctuaries along the Afghan border. There was a warning to the Pakistani leadership that, if the Pakistani military does not take significantly more aggressive action against al-Qaeda and insurgent sanctuaries in the tribal areas bordering Afghanistan, the United States will be forced to take action on its own. With Islamabad's tacit approval, Obama ordered an increase in US drone missile strikes on insurgent targets along the Pakistani border (DeYoung, 16 December 2010).

OBAMA'S VISIT TO AFGHANISTAN IN DECEMBER 2010

On 3 December 2010, Barack Obama made an unannounced visit to Afghanistan, where he personally expressed support for the troops, at a time when millions of people were thinking of a holiday of peace, not war (Feller, 3 December 2010). In a speech to 3,850 troops at Bagram Air Base, Obama declared, "You are defending your country. You are achieving your goals. You will succeed in your goals" (ABC News, 3 December 2010). During his visit, Obama visited a hospital on the base, where he met with five wounded soldiers and three wounded civilians and awarded Purple Hearts to four of them. Obama also met with surviving members of a platoon that lost six soldiers just five days ago on 29 November, when an Afghan police officer shot them during a training mission in Nangarhar province (Baker, 3 December 2010).

Obama was scheduled to meet face-to-face with President Hamid Karzai, but bad weather forced the president to abruptly cancel plans to meet with Karzai in Kabul. However, the two leaders spoke by telephone for fifteen minutes before meeting with General David Petraeus, Ambassador Carl Eikenberry, National Security Advisor Tom Donilon, and General Douglas Lute (ABC News, 3 December 2010). Canceling the face-to-face meeting with Karzai had no consequences because the President had met Karzai at a NATO meeting in Lisbon just two weeks earlier, where they adopted a plan to gradually begin handing over combat leadership to Afghan forces starting next year, with the goal of ending the foreign combat mission by 2014 (Baker, 3 December 2010).

Obama's surprise visit to war-torn Afghanistan comes ten days before he was due to address the nation on a comprehensive review of US strategy to defeat the Taliban and strengthen the Afghan government so that American troops can begin withdrawing in 2011. The visit also coincided with new problems with Karzai due to the embarrassing leaked cables published by the WikiLeaks website which described widespread fraud and corruption at the top levels of the Karzai government (NBC News 3 December 2010). However, nothing came up in the fifteen-minute phone call between Obama and Karzai (Bohan, 7 December 2010). White House officials said the review did not include any major policy changes (Klein, 02 December 2010). Unlike his last visit to Afghanistan in March 2010, when Obama pressed Karzai to root out corruption, this time the president was determined to work across departments, and White House officials said the cables did not come from calls between the presidents (Baker, 3 December 2010).

OBAMA'S EXIT PLAN

In Afghanistan, President Obama hoped to apply the 'divide and conquer formula that had worked for President George W. Bush in Iraq. But unfortunately, Afghanistan was not Iraq. Many of the conditions that created the success of the Iraq campaign were not present in Afghanistan. First, in Iraq, the United States was dealing with a more powerful and collaborative leader like Prime Minister Nouri al-Maliki. In contrast, Karzai showed that he was unable or unwilling to rein in rivals to his rule. Second, in Iraq, the United States was able to take advantage of the division between Sunni factions and Islamic extremists. In Afghanistan, there was little evidence that ethnic Pashtuns would be willing to abandon the Taliban and side with the United States (Gannon, 2011). Finally, the insurgents in Iraq did not have the same regional strongholds as the Taliban in Pakistan. Furthermore, Obama greatly disrupted the campaign by including a specific date for the start of the US troop withdrawal (Warden, spring 2013).

However, the death of bin Laden by US forces in Pakistan in May 2011 generated positive reactions around the world and was seen as a victory for the Obama administration, but his death did not mark the end of the Afghan war, as al-Qaeda continued its deadly attacks against US-led NATO forces (BBC, 3 May 2011). On 22 June 2011, Obama announced his withdrawal plan, facing growing political opposition to the Afghan war, and assured that the additional 33,000 US troops deployed to Afghanistan in 2009 will be withdrawn by the summer of 2012, or by September at the latest. The first 10,000 troops will return by the end of 2011. Obama gave his commanders 'some flexibility' on the detailed timeline for the withdrawal (Nichols, 15 July 2011). He said troop withdrawals would continue at a steady pace until the United States hands over security to Afghan authorities in 2014. After the additional troops left, there were supposed to be about 68,000 US troops until at least 2014. Obama's decision was 'a victory for Vice President Joseph R. Biden Jr.,' who had long argued for reducing military operations in Afghanistan. On the other hand, the decision to reduce troops was a setback for the US commander in Afghanistan, General David Petraeus, who was due to return to Washington as CIA chief. Petraeus refused to support Obama's decision and called for only a minimal withdrawal. He recommended limiting the withdrawal to 5,000 troops in 2011 and another 5,000 in the winter. Petraeus and other military commanders argued that eighteen months was not enough time to consolidate the fragile gains that the Americans had made in Helmand and other provinces (Landler and Cooper, 22 June 2012). Furthermore, they argued that a reduction of 10,000 troops in 2011 would create logistical problems and disrupt the summer war season (McAskill, 23 June 2011).

Defense Secretary Robert M. Gates publicly argued against a hasty troop withdrawal, although he supported Obama's decision. Secretary of State Hillary Rodham Clinton expressed objections to the level of the cuts. Republican presidential candidates, including Mitt Romney and Jon M. Huntsman Jr., were demanding a rapid troop withdrawal from Afghanistan, while Democrats complained that the cost of the war was siphoning money away from efforts to create jobs in the United States (Landler and Cooper, 22 June 2012). This announcement also had an impact on the 2012 presidential election. Opinion polls showed that a record number of Americans did not support the Afghan war. Many Democrats and some Republicans were pressuring Obama for a quick withdrawal (Terkel, 22 June 2011).

DRAWDOWN BEGINNING AND PLANS FOR ENDING THE AFGHANISTAN WAR

As part of Obama's planned withdrawal, the United States began its withdrawal on 13 July 2011, when the first unit of 650 US soldiers under the 113th Cavalry Regiment left northeastern Parwan Province, "a relatively stable area just north of Kabul". The 113th Cavalry Regiment, which arrived in November 2010, was tasked with securing the province, including the area around a major US base at Bagram. The second unit, based in Kabul, was withdrawn under the 134th Cavalry, which deployed to Afghanistan in November 2010. Their goal was to train and advise Afghan National Police units in the Kabul region (Radin, 15 July 2012).

Unlike the Bush administration, President Obama and his war advisers knew that Afghanistan could not be stabilized unless the Taliban, who played a significant role in Afghan society, were accepted as a legitimate part of future Afghan politics. In an interview with the New York Times on 8 March 2009, Obama proposed the idea of reaching out to moderate elements of the Afghan Taliban, a reflection on the tactics used by General David H. Petraeus in Iraq (Cooper and Stolberg, 7 March 2009). During the 2010 Afghanistan Conference in London, the United States supported Karzai's plan to repatriate Taliban foot soldiers when the international community requested funds to strengthen reunification efforts. The US strategy, released on 27 March 2009, promised to provide financial incentives to drain Taliban fighters and low- and mid-level commanders away from the insurgency (Fair, 2010).

In 2010–11, the United States expanded its focus from reintegration of infantry troops to reconciliation with the Taliban leadership (Sheikh and Greenwood, 2013: 06). The first direct contact between the Taliban and US officials after nine years of war began in November 2010 in Munich, Germany, where US officials met with Tayyip Agha, a trusted aide of the Taliban leader Mollah Omar, in an encounter mediated by German officials and the Qatari royal family (Borger, 8 October 2012). Subsequently, two rounds of preliminary meetings were held in Doha and Germany in 2011, and in January 2012. The Taliban's political office was informally established in Doha to negotiate with international partners. The talks held in Doha in January 2012 focused primarily on five Guantanamo detainees, including three senior commanders- Noorullah Noori, Mollah Fazel, and former interior

minister Mullah Khairullah Khairkhwa. The Afghan and Pakistani governments were not directly involved but reluctantly agreed to the talks (Sheikh and Greenwood, 2013: 06).

At the meeting, both sides agreed to transfer five Afghan Taliban prisoners from the Guantanamo Bay prison in exchange for the release of Sergeant Bowe Bergdahl, an American soldier captured by the Taliban-backed Haqqani Network in 2009. But US-Taliban talks failed due to disagreements over whether Taliban commanders released from Guantanamo in March 2012 would remain under the supervision of the Qatari government in Doha (DeYoung, 18 June 2013). On 18 April 2012, ahead of the NATO summit in Chicago in May, the United States and its NATO officials made a long-term commitment to ending the Afghan war. After a day of meetings at NATO headquarters in Brussels, they formally signed three key commitments: gradually transitioning to an Afghan-led combat role; keeping some international troops in Afghanistan beyond 2014 and providing billions of dollars a year to support Afghan security forces (Bumiller, 18 April 2012).

STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIP AGREEMENT BETWEEN THE UNITED STATES AND AFGHANISTAN (MAY 2012)

On 1 May 2012, Obama made a surprise visit to Afghanistan and met with President Hamid Karzai, with whom the United States has had a sometimes difficult relationship (Landler, 1 May 2012). According to senior Obama administration officials, the visit was timed to coincide with both presidents' desire to sign the Strategic Partnership Agreement before the NATO summit in Chicago in May 2012. However, officials acknowledged that the timing coincided with the first anniversary of the killing of Osama bin Laden (Rogin, 1 May 2012).

Following his meeting with President Karzai in Kabul, where he signed a historic agreement between the United States and Afghanistan, Obama headed to Bagram Air Base. There he met with US troops and 'thanked them for their sacrifices and those of their families in the last decade of war and paid tribute to their achievements (Curtis, 1 May 2012). Regarding the troop withdrawal, Obama noted in his speech that, "Last year, we withdrew 10,000 US troops from Afghanistan. Another 23,000 troops will leave by the end of the summer. After that, troop reductions will continue at a steady pace, with more of our troops returning home. And as our coalition has agreed, Afghans will be fully responsible for their own security by the end of 2014" (Cushman Jr., 1 May 2012). The Strategic Partnership Agreement pledged US assistance to develop the Afghan economy and government institutions for the next decade, which must be approved by Congress each year (Landler, 1 May 2012). Ultimately, through this agreement, the Obama administration wanted to build a global consensus to support peace and stability in South Asia, and Pakistan needed to be part of this process (Parrish, 2 May 2012).

CHICAGO SUMMIT AND TOKYO CONFERENCE

At the NATO summit in Chicago in May 2012, NATO leaders approved an exit plan backed by Afghan President Hamid Karzai for "irreversible change" in Afghanistan (San Diego Union-Tribune, 21 May 2012). Under the plan, the NATO-led ISAF force will hand over command of all combat missions to Afghan forces by mid-2013. Following this transition, a new and different NATO mission will advise, train and assist the expected 350,000-strong Afghan forces, and then withdraw most of the 130,000 foreign troops by the end of December 2014 (Labott and Mount, 22 May 2012). Alliance leaders announced in a summit statement that NATO will maintain a non-combat mission in Afghanistan after 2014.

In his inaugural address, President Obama thanked other Central Asian countries and Russia for their role in providing "critical transit" for supplies but did not explicitly mention Pakistan, which closed NATO ground supply lines through its territory in protest at the killing of twenty-four Pakistani soldiers in a US airstrike in November 2011 (Wilson and DeYoung, 21 May 2012). A brief discussion took place between Obama, Zardari, and Karzai on the sidelines of the summit. But Obama did not hold any formal bilateral meetings with Zardari because the issue of supply routes remained unresolved (San Diego Union-Tribune, 21 May 2012). During the summit, NATO Secretary General Anders Fogh Rasmussen confirmed that some NATO members had agreed to pay \$4 billion a year needed to fund Afghan security forces after the NATO mission ends, but he said the summit was never intended to secure that funding (Labott and Mount, 22 May 2012).

On 8 July 2012, an international donor conference held in Tokyo pledged \$16 billion for Afghanistan's economic development over the next four years to secure its future after foreign forces left in 2014. But for the first time, donor states added a condition that the Afghan government must reduce local corruption before receiving all the money. Addressing the conference, US Secretary of State Hillary Rodham Clinton said Afghan security "cannot be measured solely by the absence of war." This must be measured by improving the socio-economic conditions of the Afghan people. To achieve this goal, the Afghan government must be committed to "fighting corruption, improving governance, strengthening the rule of law, and increasing economic opportunities for all Afghans, especially women" (Perlez, 8 July 2012). Hillary Clinton did not specify how much of the \$16 billion the United States would provide, saying only that her government would maintain its funding level. After addressing the conference, Hillary Clinton met with Pakistani Foreign Minister Hina Rabbani Khar for a private discussion about Pakistan's cooperation in transporting US supplies to Afghanistan. At the meeting, she stressed the need for Pakistan to shut down the Haqqani terrorist network, which had been attacking American and NATO targets in Afghanistan (Parledge, 8 July 2012).

US SUSPENSION OF AFGHAN LOCAL POLICE FORCES TRAINING (ALP)

In 2010, as part of a larger counterinsurgency program, US forces established a new force called the Afghan Local Police (ALP) to secure rural areas in Afghanistan, where the national police force was weak. Although these Afghan recruits were not part of the main Afghan army or police, they were still considered an important stopgap for securing remote corners of Afghanistan. American special operations forces were subjected to a horrific attack by Afghans working closely with them. New intensified measures were taken to counter internal attacks, but the military did not fully understand “what was driving the attacks” (Opel Jr. and Boley, 2 September 2012).

After a series of attacks, including the killing of six Marine instructors in August 2012, General John R. Allen, the top commander in Afghanistan, called an emergency meeting of his generals to address the rising death toll. Just two days after General Allen's emergency session, two more attacks occurred, killing two Special Forces trainers and wounding two more American soldiers (Oppel Jr. and Bowley, 18 August 2012). Meanwhile, the ISAF has pledged to hand over full responsibility for the country's security to the Afghans by the end of 2014. But the internal killings were particularly worrisome as the security transition plan moved forward rapidly. Under the plan, all foreign combat troops were scheduled to leave Afghanistan by the end of 2014 (Reuters, 3 September 2012).

On 2 September 2012, in the wake of a series of so-called ‘green on blue’[†] attacks on international allies of Afghan soldiers and police, US forces announced that it will temporarily suspend training for around 1,000 new ALP recruits for at least a month to complete an intensive vetting process and 16,000 existing ALP recruits will be re-vetted (Oppel Jr. and Bowley, 2 September 2012). In his phone call with Karzai, Rasmussen outlined steps taken by NATO-led forces to stop internal attacks and called on the Afghan government to join in this effort. In response, the Afghan army detained or dismissed hundreds of soldiers accused of having ties to the insurgents and launched an investigation into the attacks, dubbed the Green-on-Blue offensive. Allen said that about a quarter of the internal killings were carried out by Taliban who had been able to infiltrate Afghan security forces (Reuters, 3 September 2012). But the Afghan government refused to say whether the detained and dismissed soldiers came from Taliban strongholds in the south and east, saying they were from all over the country (Haruni, 5 September 2012). However, Sayed Rahman, a commander in Kunar Province, blamed many attacks on soldiers from rural areas whose customs clash deeply with those of their American mentors. Some Afghan commanders said attacks were simply a product of a violent society (Oppel Jr. & Bowley, 18 August 2012).

On 18 September 2012, General John Allen suspended all joint combat operations between Afghan and American ground units in Afghanistan due to growing concerns about “insider attacks”. Under the directive of General Allen, the commander of all US forces in Afghanistan, interaction between coalition and Afghan forces will be limited to the battalion level (Munoz, 27 September 2012). However, by September 27, most US and NATO combat troops resumed joint operations with Afghan forces, because the Obama administration promised to end the current US combat mission by the end of 2014 (Whitlock, 28 September 2012).

NEGOTIATIONS OVER THE BILATERAL SECURITY AGREEMENT (BSA)

In November 2012, Afghanistan and the United States formally began their negotiations on the BSA in Kabul, in accordance with the Afghanistan-US Strategic Partnership Agreement signed in May 2012. The purpose of these discussions was to advance the goal of peace and security throughout Afghanistan, strengthen Afghan security forces, and pursue the shared goal of eliminating transnational terrorism (Roche, 3 April 2014). In January 2013, in a meeting with Hamid Karzai at the White House, President Obama said that he will set the pace for the withdrawal of US combat troops after receiving a “recommended timetable for troop reductions over the next two years” from General John Allen, the commander of US forces in Afghanistan (Wilson and Nakamura, 11 January 2013). Obama also promised to end the Afghan war “swiftly and responsibly” (Parsons and Hennessy, 11 January 2013). He said that almost all of the 66,000 US troops in Afghanistan would leave the country by the end of 2014 after which a small number of US troop will stay there.

Although Obama did not specify how many US troops would remain in Afghanistan after 2014, US officials privately said that the White House was requesting options to keep 3,000 to 9,000 troops in the country (Al Jazeera, 12 January 2013). Obama noted that any agreement on troop withdrawal must include an immunity agreement in which US troops would not be subject to Afghan law because, without an immunity agreement, the United States could face the same situation it faced when leaving Iraq. Karzai responded positively to Obama's demand, saying, “I can go to the Afghan people and argue for impunity for US troops in Afghanistan in a way that Afghan sovereignty will not be compromised, in a way that Afghan law will not be compromised” (CNN, 12 January 2013).

[†] This term refers to a color-coding system used by military forces, where blue denotes friendly forces, in this case NATO; and green denotes Afghan security forces, in this case.

OBAMA'S STATE OF THE UNION ADDRESS IN 2013

In his State of the Union address on 12 February 2013, Obama announced that approximately 34,000 US troops would leave Afghanistan by the end of 2014. He also promised that this withdrawal will continue and that the war in Afghanistan will end by the end of 2015. Obama also gave US military commanders in Afghanistan flexibility in determining the pace of troop withdrawal which will help them maintain sufficient strength for the next war season (Gordon and Landler, 12 February 2013). Obama's decision reflected the recommendation of General John R. Allen, who resigned from his post as the top US and NATO commander in Afghanistan on 10 February 2013. General Allen's "preferred option" was to withdraw 34,000 troops by February 2014. Other commanders, including General Joseph F. Dunford Jr., who took over leadership of the war from Allen, favored a slow withdrawal because it was difficult to withdraw a large number of troops in just one year. But many of the President's top civilian national security advisers, who had emphasized reducing the financial burden of the US military presence in Afghanistan, believed that withdrawing half of the troops by 2014 will leave enough forces to train the Afghan army and ensure election security (Chandrasekaran, 12 February 2013).

White House officials stressed that the 34,000-troop reduction will not adversely impact security because Afghan forces now conduct about 90 percent of military operations across the country. Under an agreement signed between Obama and Afghan President Hamid Karzai last month, Afghan forces will take over responsibility for nearly all military operations nationwide by spring. The remaining US troops will focus on training and assisting Afghan forces. A Washington Post poll found that 80% of registered voters support the president's policy of ending the war in Afghanistan (Tapper, 13 February 2013). Even Vice President Joseph R. Biden Jr. has ordered a rapid withdrawal of troops (Gordon and Landler, 12 February 2013).

In his State of the Union address, Obama made no mention of troop levels after 2014 because negotiations on a security agreement with the Afghans on maintaining a military presence after 2014 are in the early stages. However, the White House indicated its intention to keep 9,000 troops in Afghanistan after the combat mission ends (Gordon and Landler, 12 February 2013). The withdrawal announcement caused mixed reactions in Afghanistan. While the Afghan government and the Taliban welcomed Obama's decision, many Afghans were concerned about Obama's "premature decision" to withdraw US troops. They feared that a rapid troop withdrawal would destabilize Afghanistan, which was still at war with the Taliban more than 11 years after the US invasion. They also expressed concern that the roughly 352,000-strong Afghan army and police force was not prepared to take the lead in security (Fox News, 13 February 2013). Obama's decision based on recommendations from the military and his national security team, in consultation with Karzai and international coalition partners to withdraw 34,000 US troops from Afghanistan by 2014 represents a careful balance between political interests and military necessity (Gordon and Landler, 12 February 2013).

SECURITY HANDOVER FROM NATO TO AFGHAN FORCES

On 18 June 2013, as part of President Obama's announced withdrawal plan, US-led NATO forces formally handed over control of the last ninety-five districts to Afghan National Security Forces in a ceremony attended by Karzai and NATO Secretary General Anders Fogh Rasmussen. The transfer of the last ninety-five districts from NATO to Afghan control includes areas in the south and east where the Taliban concentrated their bloody insurgency since 2001 (Dawn, 18 June 2013). Although the handover ceremony did not bring about any changes on the battlefield, it marked the first time that the entire country of Afghanistan passed under the command of Afghan government forces (Peralta, 18 June 2013). Afghan President Hamid Karzai formally announced the transfer of power, saying, from here on, all security responsibilities and all security leadership will be taken over by our brave forces (Al Jazeera, 18 June 2013). NATO Chief Anders Fogh Rasmussen said that Afghan forces were completing a five-phase transition process that began in March 2011 by taking over security leadership. He said, 'we will continue to assist Afghan forces in operations as needed, but we will no longer plan, execute or lead those operations, and our combat mission will be completed by the end of 2014' (Dawn, 18 June 2013).

But the formal handover was disrupted by a suicide bombing that killed three people and injured more than twenty. Less than a week ago, a deadly suicide car bomb attack on a bus carrying Supreme Court employees in Kabul killed at least 17 people. According to officials, another forty people were injured in the June 12 blast (Al Jazeera, 18 June 2013). These attacks posed a serious challenge to the still-growing Afghan army and police forces. However, the effective response of the elite Afghan security forces to the insurgents had been widely praised as a sign of growing professionalism. General Joseph Dunford, ISAF commander, also told the BBC that Afghan forces were 'sufficiently advanced' to play their role. However, doubts about the capabilities of Afghan forces had been raised by high attrition rates and concerns about the future of foreign aid post-2014 (Dawn, 18 June 2013).

RESUME OF PEACE TALKS BETWEEN THE US AND THE TALIBAN

After informal talks broke down in January 2012, the prospect of a peaceful solution was put on ice (Sheikh and Greenwood, 2013). Yet contact between the Kabul government and Taliban representatives continued, and Washington was also ready to resume talks because it was difficult for both the United States and the Taliban to achieve their stated goals 'through arms

alone.' The Obama administration had no specific way to preserve the gains made while reducing the military presence, as it certainly should have done for financial, political, and many other reasons (Coll, 17 February 2011). The Taliban's political commission was also interested in ending the conflict through peaceful negotiations, although their military commission seemed to want to continue the war (Grossman, 8 October 2013).

On 20 May 2013, the United States received signals from the Qatari government that Taliban leaders were interested in beginning peace talks with US officials (DeYoung, Karen, 18 June 2013). Obama saw the Taliban's interest in peace talks as an opportunity that could create favorable political conditions for 'a more sustainable reduction of American troops' (Coll, 17 February 2011). On 18 June 2013, Taliban representatives confirmed to the BBC that they had opened an office in the Qatari capital, Doha, to resume talks in Qatar. This was seen as an important stage in establishing the political face of the movement. On the same day, Obama officially announced the start of formal peace talks with the Taliban in Qatar, aimed at ending the long-running war in Afghanistan. President Karzai, who had rejected peace talks with the Taliban, now agreed to talks between the Taliban and US officials on three conditions: first, the talks that began in Qatar should be immediately shifted to Afghanistan; second, the violence in Afghanistan must end through negotiations, and third, negotiations must not be used as a tool by any third party to advance its own interests in Afghanistan (De Young, 18 June 2013).

But soon the Afghan government announced that it would not participate in peace talks with the Taliban unless the process was 'Afghan-led'. Karzai changed his decision when learned that by opening an office in Doha, which was supposed to be used only as an address for peace talks, the Taliban were now trying to use that office as the political office of their government in exile. US officials tried to keep the possibility of peace talks with the Taliban alive, with assurances that America would not grant political recognition to the Taliban. But their assurances could not appease the Afghan president's anger (Brennan, 19 June 2013).

SUSPENSION OF NEGOTIATIONS ON BILATERAL SECURITY AGREEMENT

The Obama administration's duplicity so angered Karzai that on 19 June 2013, he abruptly suspended the talks, launched in November 2012, over the long term security pact with the United States, on the ground that the United States was trying to negotiate peace separately with the Taliban and their supporters in Pakistan, leaving Afghanistan's fragile government open to its enemies (Mazzetti and Rosenberg, 8 July 2013). This statement indicated that the venue for talks with the Taliban should be shifted from Qatar to Afghanistan (Usborne, 20 June 2013). Karzai said that talks will not resume until the Taliban meet directly with representatives of the Afghan government, and that it is the responsibility of the United States to convince the Taliban to negotiate with the Afghan government (Mazzetti and Rosenberg, 8 July 2013). A video conference was arranged between Obama and Karzai to defuse tensions, but it did not work out. As a result, peace talks between the Taliban and the United States failed and remained 'at an impasse' until 2020, when President Donald Trump announced direct talks with Taliban leaders (Shah and Iqbal, December 2021).

Increasingly frustrated with his treatment of President Hamid Karzai, President Obama was seriously considering accelerating the withdrawal of US troops from Afghanistan and a 'zero option' where no American troops will be there after 2014 (Mazzetti and Rosenberg, 8 July 2013). However, the 'zero option' was unlikely to become a reality in Washington's strategic interests for the following reasons.

First, a complete military withdrawal, like the American military withdrawal from Iraq, would jeopardize the gains made in Afghanistan over the past decade allowing al-Qaeda and the Taliban to regroup in parts of the country, from where they can plot against the United States and its allies (Cohen, 10 July 2013).

Second, the 'zero option' would damage US relations with its allies in the region, such as Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, which were providing land routes for supplies, fuel and other services for US bases in Afghanistan (Krishnamurthy, 19 July 2013).

Third, unlike his predecessor, Obama had a desire to 'reset' American-Russian relations. As part of his 'reset policy,' Obama was considering countering Moscow's ideas about a new comprehensive and cooperative security system through the Collective Security Treaty Organization for which Russia has been putting pressure on NATO countries several times (Rogov, 2010).

Fourth, there were reports that China was trying to build a more strategic relationship with Tehran by developing the Chabahar port in Iran that 'represents a means of connecting not only with Afghanistan and Central Asia, but also with global economic powers like India and China' (Aliasgari, 21 October 2021). Therefore, the complete withdrawal of US troops from Afghanistan may give China the opportunity to establish its dominance in Afghanistan.

Moreover, in terms of logistical operations, Afghanistan faced enormous challenges compared to the withdrawal from Iraq. Withdrawing international forces from landlocked Afghanistan, where communications were poor, by the end of December 2014 was no easier than pulling out of Iraq (BBC, 28 January 2014). The financial impact of the complete withdrawal of US troops was also quite detrimental to the Afghan economy in the coming years (Mazzetti, 8 July 2013).

DRAFT AGREEMENT ON BILATERAL SECURITY AGREEMENT

On 20 November 2013, the United States and Afghanistan reached an agreement on the final language of a bilateral security agreement, which dictates the role of US troops in Afghanistan after the withdrawal of international war troops. If ratified by Afghanistan and the United States, the agreement will take effect on 1 January 2015, and then it will remain in force until the end of 2024 and beyond unless terminated by either party with two years' prior notice (Shankar, 20 November 2013). The security agreement did not specify the final troop number after NATO's formal combat mission ended in December 2014. The number of US troops remaining in Afghanistan after 2014 had not yet been announced by the Obama administration, although the top commander in Afghanistan, Marine General Joe Dunford, privately urged the administration to keep up to 12,000 troops whereas some White House advisers argued for only 6,000 (Bengali, 20 November 2013).

BILATERAL SECURITY AGREEMENT (BSA)

The main obstacle to finalizing the BSA was Afghan President Hamid Karzai, who had "little trust" in US officials (BBC, 21 November 2013). Karzai had been opposing the signing of the agreement for months, despite it being approved by the Loya Jirga and overwhelmingly supported by the Afghan people. In November, Karzai sharply criticized US officials when he learned that at least one, and possibly two, NATO drone strikes in southern Afghanistan had killed civilians. General Joseph F. Dunford Jr., the American and NATO commander in Afghanistan spoke by phone with President Karzai and "expressed deep regret for the incident and any civilian casualties, and promised to convene an immediate joint investigation to determine all the facts of what happened" but Karzai refused to sign the agreement (Norland, 29 November 2013).

On 7 December 2013, in a meeting with US Secretary of Defense Chuck Hagel, Afghan Defense Minister Bismillah Mohammadi Khan 'expressed enthusiastic support for the bilateral security agreement' and predicted that it would 'be signed, and signed in a very timely manner'. An angry Karzai not only threatened to cancel the security agreement entirely, but he also added several new amendments to the BSA before ratification. Among these demands was an immediate and complete ban on drone strikes and unilateral counter-terrorism operations by US forces on Afghan homes, the Afghan judiciary's authority to prosecute US forces, US assistance in peace talks with the Taliban, and 'the release of Afghan prisoners held by the US at Guantanamo Bay.' Karzai not only refused to sign the agreement in late November 2013, but also stated through his spokesman that 'no minister would sign it without his approval, which he would only give if his demands were met' (Shankar, 7 December 2013).

Karzai's refusal to finalize the security agreement without further amendments frustrated US officials, who had been pushing for a deal by late 2013 so that they can begin coordinating with NATO forces for a presence in Afghanistan after 2014, if necessary. General Joseph F. Dunford Jr., the top commander of NATO and US forces in Afghanistan, who was planning a continued military presence to train, advise and assist Afghan forces beyond 2014, gave a warning to Karzai government stating that 'If the agreement is not signed by the end of this year, he will have no choice but to start more detailed planning on another reality, hinting at the so-called zero option of not having foreign troops.' General Dunford also said that a delay until next year could hinder smaller allies from building the political will domestically to commit money and personnel to a permanent military presence in Afghanistan (Shanker, 7 December 2013).

OBAMA'S SECRET VISIT TO AFGHANISTAN (25 MAY 2014)

On 25 May 2014, President Obama 'secretly' landed at Bagram Air Base, accompanied by country music singer Brad Paisley, who performed for about an hour before the president spoke to the troops. During his visit, Obama visited a base hospital and met with military officials to discuss the troop presence in Afghanistan, as the United States moves away from its longest war in Afghanistan. There was no meeting scheduled with outgoing Afghan President Hamid Karzai, 'a violent president with a troubled relationship with the White House' (Guardian, 25 May 2014). However, before leaving Afghanistan, Obama spoke with Karzai on the phone for 15 to 20 minutes. During the call, Obama praised Karzai for the progress of Afghan security forces and the recent presidential election in the country.

US officials invited Karzai to join Obama at Bagram, but the Afghan leader rejected them, saying that 'he was ready to give a warm welcome to the President of the United States in accordance with Afghan tradition, but now has no intention of meeting him in Bagram'. In his address to American troops in Afghanistan, Obama promised to bring a "responsible end" to America's longest war. He also promised, "We will ensure that Afghanistan is never again used to launch terrorist attacks against our country" (Rosenberg and Scheer, 25 May 2014). In his speech to the troops, Obama made it clear that he was 'optimistic' that he would be able to sign an agreement with the next president of Afghanistan that would see a small military presence there after 2014 (Feeney, 25 May 2014).

OBAMA'S PLAN OF DEPARTURE FROM AFGHANISTAN

On 27 May 2014, President Obama released his plan for Afghanistan, announcing that a remaining force of 9,800 US troops would remain there for one year after the end of the US combat mission in December 2014. According to the plan, this number will be halved by the end of 2015, and by the end of 2016, there will be only one investigative force in Kabul to protect the

embassy and assist Afghans with military procurement and other security-related matters (Landler, 27 May 2014). Reactions to Obama's troop reduction announcement were mixed. Republican lawmakers Senators Kelly Ayotte of New Hampshire, Lindsey Graham of South Carolina and John McCain of Arizona called Obama's plan "short-sighted" (Madhani, 27 May 2014). Senate Majority Leader Harry M. Reid (D-Nev.) said that it appropriately hands responsibility for Afghanistan's security over to the Afghan government and security forces, while at the same time maintaining our ability to aggressively defend against terrorism (DeYoung, 27 May 2014). While NATO welcomed the announcement, the Afghan military reacted to Obama's plan with skepticism, saying the Afghan army's lack of air support and heavy artillery will not be overcome by 2016 or 2017 (DeYoung, 27 May 2014).

Obama's plans were contingent on the approval of the incoming Afghan government and its willingness to sign a bilateral security agreement providing immunity for US troops serving in Afghanistan, which current Afghan President Hamid Karzai refused to sign before leaving power in September 2014. Yet the Obama administration seemed confident that the next Afghan leader would sign the joint security agreement (BBC, 27 May 2014). The two leading candidates to succeed Karzai, Abdullah Abdullah and Ashraf Ghani Ahmadzai, have expressed their support for signing the BSA if elected (Madhani, 27 May 2014). Therefore, although Washington threatened to withdraw all US forces by the end of 2014 due to Karzai's stubbornness, but it decided to wait through a long electoral deadlock until Hamid Karzai stepped down as president on 29 September 2014, when newly elected President Ashraf Ghani seeks to repair frayed ties with Washington (Al Jazeera, 1 October 2014).

However, Obama's plans were welcomed by outgoing Afghan President Hamid Karzai, who said that "the Afghan government is grateful for the support of the international community and is confident that Afghan forces, as they have done throughout history, will defend their people and territorial integrity with courage and heroism". Karzai and his officials expressed hope that the troop withdrawal could pave the way for peace talks with the Taliban, who have consistently demanded the withdrawal of foreign troops from Afghanistan (Harrison, 28 May 28 2014).

CONCLUSION OF BILATERAL SECURITY AGREEMENT (BSA)

Finally, on 30 September 2014, the United States and the new Afghan National Unity Government signed a "long-delayed" Bilateral Security Agreement (BSA) through US Ambassador James B. Cunningham and Afghan national security adviser Mohammad Hanif. On the same day, Afghanistan signed a similar agreement with NATO to allow additional foreign troops, mostly from Britain, Germany, Italy and Turkey, to remain in Afghanistan in a non-combat role after 2014. Thus, under both agreements, 9,800 American and at least 2,000 NATO troops were allowed to remain in Afghanistan after the international combat mission officially ends on 31 December 2014. The proposed bilateral security agreement included the following key points:

1. The agreement allows approximately 9,800 American troops to remain in Afghanistan after the final withdrawal of US and international combat forces after 2014, with the expectation that the number of troops will be rapidly reduced by half by 2016 (Raghavan, 30 September 2014).
2. The NATO-led ISAF mission will replace a training mission with headquarters in Kabul and six bases across the country.
3. Under the BSA, most US-led NATO forces will focus on training and supporting Afghan security forces, although some US special operations forces will remain to conduct counter-terrorism operations against remnants of al-Qaeda (Walsh and Ahmed, 30 September 2014).
4. By the end of 2015, the number of 9,800 American troops will be halved and concentrated only in Kabul and Bagram Air Base (Loyn, 30 September 2014).
5. Article 13(1) of the agreement granted legal immunity to US military forces from Afghan law, stating that Kabul agreed that "the United States will have exclusive jurisdiction over US troops committing any criminal or civil offense" in Afghanistan. However, this provision did not apply to US contractors and contractor employees (Raghavan and DeYoung, 30 September 2014).
6. Under the BSA, the United States was granted access to nine American-built military bases, which would be transferred to Afghan ownership and sovereignty after 2014 (Bengali & Zucchino, 20 November 2013).
7. Although the BSA was not a defense treaty, it stated that in the event of external aggression or the threat of external aggression, Washington and Kabul would work together to prepare an "appropriate response" including considering political, military, and economic measures (Recknagel, 30 September 2014).

While Taliban leaders have denounced the security agreement as an "attempt to establish US dominance over Afghanistan and its people," new Afghan President Ashraf Ghani welcomed the deal. He said: "Today, Afghanistan has regained its sovereignty as a power". He also said that "BSA will not violate the country's sovereignty and laws" (Loyn, 30 September 2014). He assured Afghanistan's neighbors that the increased presence of US troops would not pose any threat to them. However, from an economic perspective, the BSA was important because annual US funding for Afghanistan was 'heavily dependent on BSA approval' (Raghavan, 30 September 2014). The BSA not only reflected the implementation of the Strategic Partnership Agreement between

the two governments signed in May 2012, but also ensured the long-term presence of US and coalition forces in Afghanistan and ushers in a more stable relationship between the two countries (Michaels, 30 September 2014)

ANNOUNCEMENT OF EXPANSIVE MISSION

On 21 November 2014, President Obama authorized a broader mission for US forces in Afghanistan in 2015 than previously planned in May 2014. They were originally supposed to advise, train and assist Afghan forces and hunt down remnants of al-Qaeda. Under the President's order US forces were allowed to conduct operations against the Taliban and other militant groups that threaten American troops or the Afghan government. The new authorization allowed American jets, bombers and drones to assist Afghan forces in combat missions against the Taliban. Under the new arrangement, President Ashraf Ghani, who made an expanded American military mission much more acceptable in Afghanistan, lifted limits on US airstrikes and joint operations imposed by Hamid Karzai (Mazzetti, 21 November 2014).

The Obama administration came under criticism for the advance of Islamic State forces across northern Iraq and the collapse of the Iraqi army as a result of the rapid military withdrawal from Iraq, which left Iraqi troops unprepared to defend their country. However, the president's new arrangement in Afghanistan may alleviate some of that criticism, although some Democratic lawmakers say that Obama allowed the military to dictate the terms of the Afghanistan endgame. But no decision had been made on anything beyond 2016. According to the plan announced in May 2014, after the United States will still be able to keep military advisors in Kabul after 2016 who will work from the Security Cooperation Office of the US Embassy. But the Obama administration did not specify how large that force might be and what its exact responsibilities would be (Mazzetti, 21 November 2014).

CHANGES IN OBAMA'S PLANS IN MARCH 2015 US

On 24 March President Barack Obama welcomed new Afghan President Ashraf Ghani to the Oval Office to discuss the future of relations between the two countries. In a one-day meeting with President Obama, President Ashraf Ghani urged Obama to keep more US troops in Afghanistan. Accordingly, following the meeting, President Obama announced a planned slowdown in the pace of US troop withdrawals, maintaining the current level of 9,800 troops in Afghanistan by the end of 2015, instead of cutting the number by about half as planned in May 2014 (Lederman, 24 March 2015). Obama also promised to end the Afghan war towards the end of his presidency (Jaffe and Nakamura, 24 March 2015). This change in US plans was the result of several important factors considered by the White House. The pace of US troop withdrawal needed to be slowed in order to strengthen US counterterrorism efforts in Afghanistan.

There were fears that the Islamic State (IS) could gain a foothold in the Afghan conflict. It was essential to provide Afghan security forces with more training to counter Islamic State fighters deployed on their soil. American officials also believed that maintaining current forces in Afghanistan would allow American special operations troops and the Central Intelligence Agency to conduct covert drone strikes and other paramilitary operations in southern and eastern Afghanistan, where the insurgents were strongest and where the al-Qaeda presence was concentrated. Moreover, several influential figures, including twenty three former US ambassadors and a group of senior officials, were urging the United States to keep US troops in Afghanistan because a hasty withdrawal of US troops will lead to a repeat of what had happened in Iraq (Rosenberg, 25 March 2015).

ANNOUNCEMENT OF NEW DECISION (15 OCTOBER 2015)

But the reality in Afghanistan was different. Since 2001, the Taliban had been taking over more and more of the country. The security situation in key areas of Afghanistan remained fragile and was at risk of deteriorating in some areas. Following the fall of the city of Kunduz in northern Afghanistan, the Obama administration came under increasing pressure to abandon its previous withdrawal plan announced in May 2014. Moreover, the bitter experience of the Iraq defeat influenced Obama administration to make new decisions about Afghan strategy. So, on 15 October, after consulting with his entire national security team and Afghan partners, President Obama said that Afghan forces were not strong enough to defend their country (Rosenberg and Shear, 15 October 2015).

Obama announced a new \$15 billion annual plan to implement his new Afghan strategy. Under the new plan, the United States would maintain its current troop strength of 9,800 for most of 2016, and then begin drawing down to 5,500 by the end of the year or early 2017. US forces will maintain bases in four locations, Kabul, Bagram, Jalalabad and Kandahar, to continue counterterrorism operations against the growing Taliban threat. To reduce the cost of the Afghan war waged by his predecessor, Obama also said that by the end of 2016 he would reduce the number of US troops in Afghanistan to about 1,000, all of whom would be based in Kabul. Moreover, Obama did not forget to mention the peace talks for a political settlement as the only viable solution (Jaffe and Ryan, 15 October 2015).

CONCLUSION

Obama's policy towards Afghanistan was constructive and firmly pragmatic although his "reintegration policy towards the Taliban" was ambitious (Hoffman, 2015). In addition to defeating al-Qaeda and stabilizing Afghanistan, his administration has shown "a commitment and desire to provide democratic spaces for Afghans of all levels and ideological orientations." which was considered essential for lasting peace and stability in Afghanistan (Ra'ees, September 2010). Obama clearly understood that Afghanistan could not be stable unless the largest ethnic group, the Taliban, was accepted as a legitimate part of Afghan society. His administration was negotiating directly with the Taliban to reach a political settlement between the Afghan government and the Taliban (Landler, 1 May 2012). Obama also understood that the stability of Afghanistan was inextricably linked to Pakistan. Therefore, the two strategies adopted by his administration "linked Afghanistan's security to Pakistan's political development" (Ra'ees, September 2010). Both strategies have been called the AfPak policy, or the policy for Afghanistan and Pakistan.

Although 2009 was marked by an increase in the number of US troops in Afghanistan, in December of that year Obama announced that, by the end of July 2011, the United States would begin a conditions-based handover of responsibility to the Afghan government and security forces. In this case, President Obama kept his promise. After killing bin Laden, Obama planned to leave Afghanistan. The United States signed a bilateral security agreement with Afghanistan in 2014 to accelerate its withdrawal plans. The agreement allows about 9,800 American troops to remain in Afghanistan after the final withdrawal of US and international combat forces after 2014, with the expectation that the number of troops will be rapidly reduced in half by 2016. But he failed to stick to his latest withdrawal plan, announced in March 2015. Due to the 'uncertain' situation in Afghanistan, Obama finally decided to leave about 8,400 troops in Afghanistan through the end of his term in January 2017

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